

Shannon's Entropy and Determinism?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 14, 2025

Shannon's entropy, $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ makes use of probabilities and so it seems that it is not connected with determinism. If one has a die or coin, however, Shannon's entropy of the die is $\ln(6)$ and of the coin, $\ln(2)$. \ln is simply a math function which is not linked to either determinism or stochasticity and 6 and 2 are simply descriptions of the number of sides of the die or coin. Thus the Shannon entropy number itself does not necessarily imply a statistical situation, at least in the case of $p(i)$ being a uniform distribution.

In the case of a coin or die toss, the statistical nature of the process appears in the details of the toss because one may have HHTTT etc even though $p(H)=.5$, $p(T)=.5$. Shannon's entropy, however, is linked with a large number of runs such that overall one has the same number of heads as tails and details like HHTTT etc are not captured in $\ln(2)$, we argue. Furthermore, if one tosses two objects, then the \ln (for $p(i)$ represented by a uniform distribution) combines the intrinsic information of each object, retaining the identity of the object. This is more like book-keeping and not necessarily associated with randomness or uncertainty. Certainly a uniform distribution is a type of probability distribution, but for such a case, Shannon's entropy is about describing information of the system (with each being on the same footing). In such a description, there is no intrinsic uncertainty.

In (1), we argued that one may apply the first law of thermodynamics to a deterministic particle bouncing back and forth in a 1-D container of length L with constant speed. We found that a statistical description arises not because of indeterminism of the system (it is deterministic), but because of removal of information. Pressure acting at all times means one must use time units of a cycle time and this implies losing the detailed time measurements of $x=vt$. We found in (1) that a 1-D Sackur-Tetrode entropy formula holds which is proportional to $\ln(T \text{ power } .5) + \ln(L)$. $T=mvv$ and so is a completely deterministic quantity. Thus $T \text{ power } .5 = \sqrt{m} v$ which is simply deterministic information in the system and not linked with probability. $T dS/dT \rightarrow T \ln(T \text{ power } .5)$ removes T from the denominator, leaving dT which is simply a change in deterministic information. On the other hand, dL/L does have a probabilistic interpretation as increasing the length L by dL means that one is more uncertain of the position of the particle because the pressure time units of the order of cycle time mean that one does not follow a particle as $x=vt$. Again, it seems that entropy contains some deterministic features and may be more related to information than to probability/stochasticity/fluctuations.

Shannon's Entropy

Shannon's entropy is:

$$-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i)) \quad ((1))$$

Given that ((1)) contains probabilities $p(i)$, one immediately thinks of a stochastic system. For example, one may apply ((1)) to a coin or die toss. These are considered stochastic because one has no idea what value will appear in a single toss. The issue, however, is that ((1)) is

linked to probabilities which are uniform and based on $N \rightarrow$ infinite trial runs and there is no longer any uncertainty in these. For instance, a coin has two sides and a die, six. This is a description, i.e. information, and has nothing to do with probability. These properties hold whether the coin or die are tossed or not. The use of $p(i)$ simply describes these in the uniform probability case and so:

$$- \ln(.5) = \ln(2) \quad \text{and} \quad - \ln(1/6) = \ln(6) \quad ((2))$$

((2)) may be interpreted as strictly the \ln of physical attributes (information) about a coin or die and does not necessarily need to pertain to any tossing or uncertainty or short term randomness. Certainly after $N \rightarrow$ infinite tosses, one knows how many of each attribute results one has. The randomness is in the exact sequence in which they appear, but this randomness has nothing to do with the Shannon entropy result ((2)).

As an example, we consider two six-sided dice. The first mimics a coin in that it can only have two values H, or T, so three sides are labeled H, and the other three, T. The second die is a normal one. One may then toss the first die followed by the second etc. Then, Shannon's entropy is:

$$\ln(2) + \ln(6) = \ln(12) \quad ((3))$$

In this case, one has the 6 numbers of the usual die and 3 H's and 3 T's from the die mimicking a coin in order to obtain the number 12. Alternatively, one may toss a real coin followed by the die and the same result ((3)) appears because a cycle of the die involves 6 tosses while a cycle of the coin, only 2. Thus, a cycle of a die involves three cycles of a coin. The use of the \ln in Shannon's entropy allows this cycling feature of the information to appear, whereas:

$$2+6 = 8 \quad \text{i.e. 8 physical possible results: H, T, 1,2,3,4,5,6} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, Shannon's entropy is related to physical results and cycling frequency it seems, but not necessarily probability. For example, one may have a set of 12 cards in a particular order. One may then state that:

$$\ln(12) \text{ is Shannon's entropy } ((5))$$

There is nothing probabilistic about this, it seems. We now give another viewpoint which applies to the coin and die information, but also to other correlated two objects, each with their own information.

The next example is the tossing of two dice. This leads to:

$$\ln(6)+\ln(6) = \ln(36) \quad ((4))$$

Here, it seems that one considers possible arrangements of values of each die, with each die retaining its identity. (This view may also be applied to the coin and die toss.) The two objects

are then correlated and one does not simply look at the numerical values, but keeps the information about the identity of each die. Thus, a complete set is 36, but this is bookkeeping. This, however, does not necessarily mean that one has randomness or uncertainty. One may have a rule that one writes down a 1 one from the first die, then 1,2,3... from the second, followed by 2 from the first die and 1,2,3.. From the second again. This leads to a sequence of 36 pairs, but is a completely deterministic recipe. In other words, one seems to be counting information or in the case of two objects, information pairs. Thus, Shannon's entropy seems to be about information, including information about the identity of an object as well its intrinsic information, and not so much about randomness, it seems. The notion of information and probability seems to appear for these uniform probability examples, when one considers that each information pair maps to a possible physical outcome in some scenario. Then, there is probability. This is certainly a possibility, but one may also argue, it seems, that Shannon's entropy is a way of counting information and then taking the \ln of it. In such a view, there is no randomness or uncertainty, at least in the case of $p(i)$ following a uniform distribution.

First Law of Thermodynamics Applied to a Deterministic Problem

In (1), we tried to argue that the first law of thermodynamics may be applied to a strictly deterministic problem, namely a particle with constant speed v bouncing back and forth in a 1-D container of length L . We argued that statistical features arise if one introduces the concept of pressure as a time average using time units equal to cycle lengths. This means that one removes time measurements within a cycle, but these are needed for $x=vt$ and so one has no idea where the particle is. This loss of information does lead to a probabilistic description in position, but the motion remains deterministic nevertheless.

We argued in (1) that the entropy (1-D) is of the form:

$$S \text{ proportional to } \ln(L) + \ln(T \text{ power } .5) \text{ where } T = mv^2 \quad ((5))$$

Then, TdS goes as: dL/L ((6)) if T is held constant. This is probabilistic because of the probability linked with position.

On the other hand: $T \frac{dS}{dT} dT = .5 dT$ is deterministic and equal to $dE = .5 dT$.

$E = .5mv^2 = .5 T$ and so changing the deterministic T , i.e. v (speed), changes E . The T in $T dS$, together with the deterministic $\ln(T \text{ power } .5)$ represent a change behaviour in $T dS$, but not necessarily any randomness. T is simply deterministic information.

Thus, we suggest one must be careful in interpreting entropy as only linked with uncertainty or randomness.(or even disorder as is sometimes suggested).

Conclusion

In conclusion, even though Shannon's entropy is written in terms of probabilities: $-\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$, this does not mean that it has to necessarily be viewed in terms of randomness or uncertainty, at least in the case of $p(i)$ representing a uniform distribution. In such a case, it

describes, for a single object, \ln of various information states, e.g. $\ln(2)$ for a coin and $\ln(6)$ for a die. If one correlates two objects, then the \ln allows one to combine each attribute from one with each attribute from the second one etc, i.e. $\ln(a) + \ln(b) = \ln(ab)$. This may be applied, in the case of a uniform distribution, to probability outcomes with equal weight, but we suggest it may also be interpreted as \ln of basic information without the need for a probabilistic interpretation.

In particular, in (1) we describe a completely deterministic system of a single particle with constant speed v in a 1-D container of length L . We argue that introducing pressure means using time units of a cycle length and so one loses time measurements needed for $x=vt$. Thus, one does not know the location of the particle and may use a probabilistic approach for position. Energy, however, is $.5mv^2$. One may call this $.5 T$ ($T=mv^2$), but then an entropy expression follows the Sackur-Tetrode 1-D form: $\ln(L) + \ln(T \text{ power } .5)$. The T portion is completely deterministic, it seems, and related to information and not randomness or uncertainty, we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Ideal Gas Law, Sackur-Tetrode Formula and First Law of Thermodynamics for a Deterministic System? (preprint, zenodo, 2025)